

Exploring the Relationship Between Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intentions among Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists

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Background

- High turnover intentions of 37.6% and subsequent turnover rates (13.6%) among CRNAs.
- Factors influencing turnover intentions: job satisfaction, organizational commitment, work-life balance, job security, and career growth opportunities.
- Consequences include increased workload/stress, decreased quality of care, longer wait times, and higher risk of adverse events.
- Cost implications for healthcare organizations due to CRNA turnover (\$150,000 per new hire).

Purpose

- The study investigated factors associated with job satisfaction and their potential associations with turnover intentions among CRNAs working at a large healthcare organization in Southern California.
- To provide valuable insights to promote job satisfaction and reduce turnover intentions among CRNAs within Southern California healthcare organizations with multiple hospitals.

Review of Literature

Job Satisfaction Factors:

- Influenced by work environment and autonomy levels.
- Positive work environments linked to higher job satisfaction in healthcare (Kibwana et al., 2018; Han et al., 2018).

Turnover Intention Significance :

- Crucial predictor of turnover, impacting organizations negatively (Kol et al., 2018).
- Demographic factors (age, education, marital status, gender) and job characteristics (stress, satisfaction, commitment) influence turnover intentions (Kassa & Bedada, 2021; Venegas et al., 2023).

Critical Need for Understanding

- Essential for retention and well-being of healthcare workers.
- Limited studies on specific factors influencing job satisfaction and turnover intentions among CRNAs within a single organization.

Methods

Design and Participants

- Used a cross-sectional design with 430 CRNAs from Southern California Kaiser Permanente.
- The study was approved by CSUF and KP Institutional review board

Data Collection/Analysis

- Email invitations to participate in the study were sent via KPNAA; participants provided electronic consent.
- Survey covered demographics, job satisfaction (MNPJSS), and turnover intentions (TIS-6).
- Collected data over five weeks with a reminder email during week two.
- Analyzed using descriptive statistics for demographics and inferential statistics (correlations, regression), R statistical package version 4.3.1 (<https://www.r-project.org>) to identify factors influencing job satisfaction and turnover intentions among CRNAs.

Results

Demographics

- Data collected from 60 CRNAs, response rate of 14%.
- Majority were female, aged ranged between 31-60, with varying shift lengths.

Turnover Intentions

- Turnover Intention Survey (TIS-6) showed 30% intending to leave.
- The turnover intention correlational matrix identified high correlation among the six turnover intention items.
- Overall composite score was 2.9 out of 5.
- Turnover intentions varied based on experience, higher among less experienced CRNAs, lowest among over 30 years experienced. (see Figure 1).

Figure 5 Association between Marital Status and Job satisfaction

Table 2. Summary statistics of the turnover intention items (N=60).

Item	Mean (SD)
1) How often do you consider leaving your job?	2.7 (1.2)
2) How satisfying is your job in fulfilling your personal needs?	2.8 (1.0)
3) How often are you frustrated when not given the opportunity at work to achieve your personal goals?	2.4 (1.0)
4) How often do you dream of getting another job that will better suit your personal needs?	3.0 (1.3)
5) How likely are you to accept another job at the same compensation level should it be offered to you?	3.1 (1.5)
6) How often do you look forward to another day at work?	3.6 (1.2)
7) Overall	2.9 (1.0)

Jobs Satisfaction

- Job Satisfaction mean score was 174; males reported slightly higher satisfaction (177) than females (173).
- Job satisfaction lowest among never married individuals (see Figure 5).
- Intrapractice Partnership/Collegiality and Challenge and Autonomy to had the lowest score among the jobs satisfaction subscales.
- Multivariate model demonstrated high explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.82$), (See table 3).

Table 3. Summary statistics of the fit of the best explanatory model*.

Satisfaction item	Effect	SE	t-value	p-value
Satisfaction with immediate supervisor	-0.15	0.04	-3.34	0.002
Satisfaction with patient scheduling policies and practices	-0.34	0.07	-4.69	<.001
Sense of accomplishment	-0.32	0.07	-4.82	<.001
Interaction with other NPs including faculty	-0.14	0.07	-2.12	0.04
Flexibility in practice protocols	-0.18	0.05	-3.34	0.002

*This model attained an R^2 of 0.82.

Discussion

- Response rate comparable studies: Negusa et al. (8%), Mahoney et al. (9.3%), Lea et al. (3.2%).
- 30% participants inclined to transition, aligning with Dexter et al. (37.6%)
- Overall, CRNAs reported high job satisfaction; males scored slightly higher than females, echoing observations from prior studies (Negusa et al., 2021; Venegas et al., 2023).
- Overall job satisfaction score lower than a study encompassing CRNAs and other APPs, indicating potential geographical and institutional differences (Venegas et al., 2023).
- Areas of concern include emphasizing the critical role of administrative support, supervisor relationships, and compensation in job satisfaction, consistent with existing literature (Dexter et al., 2021; Kassa & Bedada, 2021; Kibwana et al., 2018).

Recommendation

- Provide targeted support for novice CRNAs and unmarried individuals with higher turnover intentions.
- Employ strategies like enhancing supervisor support, refining patient scheduling, promoting accomplishment, fostering CRNA interactions, and providing flexible practice protocols to address turnover intentions
- Cultivate a supportive workplace encouraging collaboration, autonomy, and professional growth to boost job satisfaction and reduce turnover intentions.

Limitation

- Low response rates, limited methods of reaching participants.
- Length of survey with 57 questions
- Incomplete responses.
- Method of dissemination, infrequently checked emails.
- Survey intended audience for NPs, may not accurately address specific CRNA factors.

Reference

